

SITE GPR	YEAR 11	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.410 Max: 62.577	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1431 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 1894-98 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION
cut for SW 1429 (stone vessel)

Covered by xSU: 0, 1446 Fills SU: Filled by xSU: 1432

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED?
 Color Composition Compaction

FORMATION PROCESS
 Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% <input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Soft <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original

Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1446	Covers:
Is cut by:	Cuts: 1001 (bedrock), 1424
Is filled by: 1431, 1429, 1430	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS
SU is still in situ

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: positioned near the southern extent of Area B, located to the west of center to the south of SU 1424

Shape: irregular oval

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:

Cut edges: rounded straight

Cut sides: straight concave convex sloping

Cut bottom: flat concave irregular

How is cut top edge? sharp rounded

How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded

Observations: circular cut made for large stone vessel 1429

NOT EXCAVATED
top of cut only →

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

cut for vessel 1429
 not excavated in GPR II, potentially excavated by previous excavation
 cut is covered by SU 1446 in the NW corner, where space between
 the cut and the bedrock is the widest, cut walls are entirely bedrock.
 cut abuts the bedrock that defined the bottom (depth) of SU 1424

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

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